

METHOD OF COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION ON DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS OF NOTCHED CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The method of computational simulation on deformation and fracture characteristics of notched cross-ply laminates has been developed on the basis of micromechanics. By use of the Weibull weakest link theory with respect to fiber strength, the tension-softening relation of the laminates is first derived, and then the macroscopic fracture energy of the laminates is determined. The extension-stop behavior of the macroscopic crack in the laminates is considered from the viewpoint of the balance of the fracture energy and the released energy. As numerical examples, the computational simulation of the load-displacement curves including load drops at the maximum load level was carried out for a notched cross-ply CFRP laminate. Finally, the load-displacement curves were predicted for various values of the debond stress of fiber bundles.

Keywords: cross-ply laminate, notch, fracture, load-displacement curve, computational simulation, micromechanics, probabilistic model, tension-softening relation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the Mode I type progressive fracture of notched CFRP laminates has been well studied (for example, References [1-5]). These studies can be classified into two groups according to the models used. One is the stiffness reduction model [1-3] and the other the fictitious crack model [4, 5].

In fracture toughness tests, actually, the notched cross-ply CFRP laminates deform nonlinearly before a macroscopic crack initiation, and the extension-stop behavior of the macroscopic crack occurs at the maximum load level. However, the sufficient explanation of load-displacement curves including load drops at the maximum load level has not been presented. With respect to the pull-out fiber bundles on the fracture surface, Wells and Beaumont [6] obtained the distribution of the pull-out length of fiber bundles, in assuming that the fiber bundles behave as thick fibers. Beaumont [7] has also stated that there is a good correlation between the pull-out length and the fracture energy of the laminates.

In this study, in view of these facts, the method of computational simulation on deformation and

fracture characteristics of notched cross-ply laminates has been developed. First of all, the tension-softening relation of the laminates is derived on basis of the Weibull weakest link theory with respect to fiber strength, and then the macroscopic fracture energy of the laminates is determined. The extension-stop behavior of the macroscopic crack in the laminates is considered from the viewpoint of the balance of the fracture energy and the released energy. As numerical examples, the computational simulation of the load-displacement curves was carried out for a notched cross-ply CFRP laminate. Finally, the load-displacement curves were predicted for various values of the debond stress of fiber bundles.

2. THEORY

2.1 Damage formation process

The damage is formed at a notch tip in cross-ply laminates. The damage formation process is schematically shown in Figure 1. With applied load increasing, cracks extend from the notch tip in 90° plies which are normal to the applied load direction, and then the delaminations between the plies initiate from the crack surfaces and tend to grow on both sides with respect to the cracks. With the load further increasing, several fiber bundles in 0° plies break. At last, almost all of the bridging fiber bundles in 0° plies break and a macroscopic crack extends.

2.2 Cumulative probability of the pull-out length in the scatter of the debond stress

Consider bridging fiber bundles. The debonding of the fiber bundle occurs when the tensile stress in the fiber bundle at the position of the tip of the debonding region attains the debond stress σ_d . We assume that no frictional forces act on the debonding surface. In this case, the tensile stress in the fiber bundle is equal to the debond stress along the debonding region and the fiber bundle

Figure 1. Schematic view of damage formation process.

necessarily breaks at the tip of the debonding region [8]. If the strength distribution of the fiber bundle can be expressed in the form of the Weibull distribution, the cumulative probability of the pull-out length of the fiber bundle $F'_p(l_p, \sigma_d)$ is given by

$$F'_p(l_p, \sigma_d) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -2l_p \left(\frac{\sigma_d}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right\} \quad (1)$$

where l_p is the pull-out length, and σ_0 and m are, respectively, the scale parameter and the shape parameter of the Weibull distribution. It should be here noted that the debonding grows symmetrically with respect to the cracks in 90° plies. In this study, we assume that the debond stress is scattered and the distribution of the debond stress is expressed by the normal distribution. Then the cumulative probability of the pull-out length of the fiber bundle $F_p(l_p)$ is written as

$$F_p(l_p) = \int_0^\infty F'_p(l_p, \sigma_d) f_h(\sigma_d) d\sigma_d \quad (2)$$

where $f_h(\sigma_d)$ is the probability density function of the normal distribution of the debond stress.

2. 3 Tension-softening relation and fracture energy

When a fictitious crack is substituted for the damage zone, the cohesive stress acting on the fictitious crack surfaces σ_c is approximately estimated by the probabilistic expectation of the tensile load acting on the bridging fiber bundles per unit crack area. The opening displacement of the fictitious crack surfaces u_c is estimated by the elongation of the debonding fiber bundles in 0° plies. The relationship between the cohesive stress σ_c and the crack opening displacement u_c is called tension-softening relation.

Consider fiber bundles bridging the fictitious crack surfaces. In i th fiber bundle, the debond stress is denoted by σ_{di} and the pull-out length by l_{pi} . The tensile stress in the i th fiber bundle retains σ_{di} until the crack opening displacement u_c becomes $u_c = 2l_{pi}\sigma_{di}/E_L$. Here E_L is Young's modulus of the fiber bundle in the fiber direction. Then the tension-softening relation, which is the relationship between σ_c and u_c , can be expressed by the following equation.

$$\sigma_c(u_c) = A_f \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{di} H \left(\frac{2l_{pi}\sigma_{di}}{E_L} - u_c \right) \quad (3)$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function, A_f is the cross sectional area of each fiber bundle and n is the number of the fiber bundles per unit fictitious crack area.

The area enclosed with the tension-softening curve and the horizontal and vertical axes gives the fracture energy of the laminates. From Equation 3, the fracture energy per unit crack area W is given by

Figure 2. Geometry of compact tension specimen.

$$W = A_f \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2l_{pi}\sigma_{di}^2}{E_L} \quad (4)$$

In the numerical calculation, random numbers for σ_{di} and l_{pi} are generated so as to realize that the distributions of the generated random numbers are identical with the distributions of σ_d and l_p .

2. 4 Extension-stop condition of macroscopic crack

Fracture energy is consumed by macroscopic crack extension. On the other hand, elastic strain energy stored in the laminates is released with the macroscopic crack extension. In this study, the extension-stop behavior of the macroscopic crack in the laminates is simulated by comparing the fracture energy with the released strain energy. If the fracture energy is less than the released strain energy, the macroscopic crack extends. On the contrary, if the fracture energy is greater than the released strain energy, the macroscopic crack stops. The fracture energy is obtained from Equation 4 and the released strain energy is calculated by using FEM.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiment was conducted with a cross-ply CFRP laminate made of Mitsubishi Rayon ETIS/#340 prepreg. The nominal thickness is 0.125 mm and the fiber volume fraction is 55 %. The stacking sequence of the laminate is $[0/90]_{10s}$. The compact tension specimen was machined from the laminate (Figure 2). The width of the specimen is 62.5 mm and the initial notch length is 25 mm. The notch root radius is 0.25 mm.

The fracture toughness test was carried out with an Instron testing machine at a cross head speed of

Figure 3. Load P -crack mouth displacement V_M curves.

Figure 4. Cumulative probability of pull-out length.

0.2 mm/min. During the test, the load P and crack mouth displacement V_M were measured. The load-crack mouth displacement curve obtained is shown by the solid line in Figure 3. It can be seen from the figure that nonlinear behavior appears from the half of the maximum load level and several load drops occur at the maximum load level.

The pull-out length of the fiber bundles in 0° plies was measured from the observation by SEM. In Figure 4, the experimental data are shown by the open circles, which give the cumulative

probability F_p versus the pull-out length l_p . The cumulative probability increases monotonically with the pull-out length and the increasing rate of the cumulative probability decreases with the pull-out length increasing.

4. RESULTS OF COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Determination of the distribution of debond stress

The average value σ^* and standard deviation V of the debond stress were determined by best fitting Equation 2 to the measured cumulative probability of the pull-out length. The scale parameter σ_0 and the shape parameter m were taken as $\sigma_0=2.5$ GPa and $m=13$. From the observation of the fracture surface, the cross section of the pull-out fiber bundles was assumed to be the square with a side 0.25 mm. Then, the values of σ^* and V were obtained as $\sigma^*=4.40$ GPa and $V=0.22$ GPa. The best fitting curve is shown in Figure 4 by the solid line.

4.2 Results of computational simulation

As mentioned in Chapter 3, the load-crack mouth displacement curve indicates significant nonlinearity before the maximum load level, which may be attributed to the nonlinearity of the shear modulus. In the computational simulation, this fact was taken into account. That is, tangent shear modulus G'_{xy} , which is the function of the shear strain γ_{xy} , was given by

$$G'_{xy}(\gamma_{xy}) = \begin{cases} 3.2 \text{ GPa} & (0 \leq \gamma_{xy} < 1.65 \times 10^{-3}) \\ G_i + \alpha(1 - n_1 \gamma_{xy}) \exp(-n_1 \gamma_{xy}) \text{ GPa} & (1.65 \times 10^{-3} \leq \gamma_{xy} < 5.4 \times 10^{-2}) \\ 0.0845 \text{ GPa} & (5.4 \times 10^{-2} \leq \gamma_{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where G_i , α and n_1 are, respectively, $G_i=0.498$ GPa, $\alpha=3.07$ GPa and $n_1=37.0$. Young's moduli of the cross-ply CFRP laminate E_x and E_y , Poisson's ratios ν_x and ν_y , and Young's modulus of the fiber bundles in the fiber direction E_L were taken as $E_x=E_y=59.5$ GPa, $\nu_x=\nu_y=0.038$ and $E_L=129$ GPa. Here the coordinate axes x, y coincide with the fiber directions of the cross-ply laminate.

Three typical results of the computational simulation of the load-crack mouth displacement curve, which are in the same condition, are shown in Figure 3. As can be seen from the figure, the deformation behavior before the macroscopic crack initiation are in good agreement with the experimental result. Several load drops at the maximum load level are also observed on the computational simulation curves. It could be found that the computational simulation curves show the similar tendency with the experimental result.

4.3 Prediction of load-crack mouth displacement curves

In this section, we examine the load-crack mouth displacement curves for various values of the debond stress of fiber bundles. The computational simulation of the load-crack mouth displacement curves were carried out for the average values of the debond stress which are 2 % lower or higher

Figure 5. Prediction of load-crack mouth displacement curves.

than the reference value mentioned in the previous section. For the other material constants, the same values were used. The results are shown in Figure 5. The maximum load increases (decreases) about 11~14 % with the debond stress decreasing (increasing) 2 %. It can be emphasized that the maximum load is sensitive to the debond stress.

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